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СЕРТИФИКАЦИЯ АВИАЦИОННОЙ ПРОДУКЦИИ И ОБОРУДОВАНИЯ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Рассмотрены особенности сертификации сложных технических систем, в частности, авиационной техники (АТ) в Республике Узбекистан и за рубежом. Анализируется принцип «сквозной» сертификации при проектировании летательных аппаратов (ЛА), использование методов валидации и проверки.

Ключевые слова: обязательная сертификация; порядок сертификации, процедуры валидации, летные испытания; управление качеством; стендовые испытания; процедуры проверки.

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CERTIFICATION OF AVIATION PRODUCTS AND EQUIPMENT

ANNOTATION

The features of certification of complex technical systems, in particular, aviation equipment (AT) in the Republic of Uzbekistan and abroad are considered. The principle of "end-to-end" certification in the design of aircraft (AC), the use of validation and verification methods are analyzed.

Keywords: mandatory certification; procedure for certification, validation procedures, flight tests; quality management; bench tests; verification procedures.

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AVIATION MAHSULOTLARI VA USKUNALARINI SERTIFIKATLASH

ANNOTATSIYA

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi va xorijda murakkab texnik tizimlarni, xususan, aviatsiya texnikasini (AT) sertifikatlash xususiyatlari ko‘rib chiqiladi. Samolyotlarni loyihalashda (AC) "uchdan uchgacha" sertifikatlash printsipli, validatsiya va tekshirish usullaridan foydalanish tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: majburiy sertifikatlash; sertifikatlashtirish tartibi, tasdiqlash tartiblari, parvoz sinovlari; sifat menejmenti; dastgoh sinovlari; tekshirish tartiblari.

The requirements and procedures for type certification are defined in the Aviation Regulations of the Republic of Uzbekistan, State Record of Experimental Aircraft (AR RUz 46). Newly designed aircraft samples must comply with the airworthiness standards (AAS) in force at the date of acceptance of the application, any additional requirements the certification body considers necessary to ensure safety.

Once compliance with the NVL has been established, a type certificate is issued to the organization responsible for the type design, clearly stating those airworthiness standards which have been met and which provided the regulatory basis for the issuance of the certificate. In general, these standards continue to apply to specific instances of aircraft or components manufactured in accordance with this design document.

Thus, according to the VC, all aircraft, their engines and component parts are required to be certified.

On the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, certification of aviation equipment has been delegated to the Interstate Aviation Committee (IAC). It is a permanent body. A special body, the Aviation Register (Aviaregister), has been established to carry out its activities. Certificates are issued by the Aviaregister.

It is now generally accepted that certification is one of the most effective forms of ensuring the quality of products or services and their competitiveness in domestic and foreign markets.

The multifunctionality of the certification field requires the development of an appropriate infrastructure - certification bodies and accredited testing laboratories.

Certification is particularly important for complex technical systems (CTS), whose failures often have severe consequences. The forms and methods of certification of complex products differ from traditional approaches used in the certification of simpler equipment. For example, certification of audio- and video equipment does not require verification of reliability indicators as part of certification tests, while for aircraft equipment verification of reliability indicators is mandatory and of paramount importance. Thus, the specifics of certification of complex systems should be the subject of special study.

There are differences in approaches to STS certification in the field of aircraft construction between leading foreign firms in France, England, USA and domestic aircraft enterprises. In this regard, it may be noted that there is a problem of harmonisation of procedural certification requirements (AP RUz 46 and others) with their foreign counterparts in the civil aviation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. A number of important and effective norms and procedures of the Soviet period have been lost (e.g. the role of head research institutes of the industry), while useful foreign norms and procedures have been missed (in particular, on the procedure for certification and circulation of aircraft components).

Flight test methods based on objective acquisition of a wide range of information and flight crew evaluation play an extremely important role in domestic certification practice. Flight tests are widely used in our practice during aircraft design and certification and include investigations on test benches, flying laboratories and the aircraft being certified. One of the important tasks here is (as an element of unit and system certification) the development of unit and system type test standards. Implementation of advanced technical requirements necessitated new materials and coatings, substantial revision of testing procedures and methods, prototyping of aircraft and their testing prior to installation on aircraft, expansion and development of the testing facilities to perform full-scale testing of products, enhancement of information support of new developments, and specialisation of

production. The on-board equipment technical level indicators are confirmed at the stage of testing in the course of development work. To put this principle into practice, the leading research institutes together with the Design Bureau have developed and approved standards for reliability testing of avionics units and systems.

At present, in a number of cases, reliability indicators of airborne equipment at the stage of development are confirmed by design values. The test standards require validation of reliability indicators of onboard equipment at the stage of development to 0.6 of the calculated value, which will reduce the time of flight testing of aircraft to 2-3 years instead of 6-7 years in the current practice. All this can be achieved through bench tests (Fig. 1) [1].

In order to confirm that the characteristics of the products meet advanced technical requirements, industry certification (certification) of units and systems of on-board equipment has been introduced.

Figure 1. Schematic of Equivalent Cyclic Bench Tests (ECB) of aircraft and helicopter equipment with complex reproduction of loads as close as possible to real operating conditions (REU)

A set of NDs has been developed that establishes the procedure for carrying out work in the industry to improve the technical level of AT products and the procedure for industry certification of aircraft and engine on-board equipment.

These documents define the organization and procedure of work in the industry, the functions of the participants of the work and their interaction, they provide for permanent control of the leading thematic institute over the development, testing and operation of on-board equipment and the issuing of a certificate of eligibility of on-board equipment for use in aircraft.

However, the bulk of certification work is carried out during flight tests of prototype aircraft and helicopters. At the same time, there is virtually no effective system of certification and control over the activities of designers and manufacturers (suppliers) of component parts and components.

The current stage of quality management development is characterized by a shift in emphasis from the control of finished products to the control and management of manufacturing processes. This trend is embodied in the ISO 9000 series of international standards. However, in the creation of the quality management system of aviation industry enterprises, one cannot ignore the fact that their universality does not allow the necessary degree to reflect the specifics of creating aviation equipment, which are highly integrated complex digital systems.

Analysis of foreign experience in quality management has shown that, firstly, certification is a powerful means of quality assurance, and secondly, quality management methods are only effective

when they are applied at all levels of the organization, from the designer to senior management. Therefore, it is relevant for domestic manufacturers to use foreign experience of implementing system and process approaches in design practice, taking into account the advantages of the so-called "end-to-end" certification with the participation of all specialists involved in the full life cycle of aviation products [2].

For aircraft on-board systems, the process and system approach is most fully embodied in foreign documents, notably DO-254 [3], which most fully defines hardware complexity: "An item of hardware is defined as simple only if an extensive combination of deterministic checks and analyses can ensure correct functional performance under all anticipated operating conditions without behavioral anomalies. When an item cannot be classified as simple, it shall be classified as complex.

From the definitions of simple and complex elements, it follows that deterministic methods of analysis are not sufficient, which logically necessitates the use of statistical approaches.

The key to providing design assurance is a systematic approach to the design of aircraft on-board equipment. Design assurance refers to a process consisting of specifically planned systematic activities that together provide assurance that errors or omissions in requirements or design are identified and corrected so that the implemented system will meet certification requirements.

The typical approach to the design of functional EE systems begins with conceptual design and ends with certification. For most complex systems, proof of design assurance is carried out over most of the design period, i.e. the certification process is regarded as a design support process.

The purpose of the certification process is to prove that the aircraft and its systems comply with airworthiness standards.

One of the means of certifying highly integrated and complex systems is the need to use design assurance methods, so it is recommended that coordination between the applicant and the certification body be ensured as early as possible (before the project is implemented). Conformity assessment methods are proposed by the applicant and the certification body determines the sufficiency of the data to prove conformity.

Table 1 shows the possible certification data of the system. The safety assessment process provides analytical evidence of compliance with airworthiness requirements. It includes specific assessments, corrected during the system design process and linked to other processes supporting its design.

The objectives of the validation process are to check that the requirements are correct (no ambiguities or formulation errors) and complete (no omissions or inclusions of non-essentials). Validation of requirements and assumptions at higher levels serves as the basis for validation at lower levels.

Table 1

List of system certification data [2]

Certification plan	Design plan Architecture and design Requirements Validation plan Verification plan Configuration management plan Process Assurance Plan
Configuration pointer	Functional risk assessment Preliminary system safety assessment System security assessment Analysis of common causes of failure Validation data Verification data Evidence of configuration management Evidence of process assurance
Certification report	

Most design programmes have a number of assumptions that cannot be directly proven to be correct. These assumptions are: environmental and operational; related to design, manufacturing, manufacturability and equipment installation. Expertise, analysis and testing are used to validate the assumptions, as well as demonstrating that the system architecture limits the consequences of an

erroneously accepted assumption.

The main validation methods are requirements tracing, analysis, modelling, ad hoc testing, performance simulation, similarity analysis, and engineering assessments.

Separate validation methods may also be used for verification at the same time. In this case, the validation and verification plans must be coordinated.

The verification process ensures that the implemented system meets the requirements of the validated system. Four main methods can be used to verify any system or product: inspection and peer review, analysis and modelling, testing, operating experience.

The analysis of foreign approaches and procedures for AVIATION product certification shows that the main distinguishing feature of foreign design technology is the certification orientation of all types of work, starting from the conceptual design stage, i.e. the application of the so-called 'end-to-end' certification principle.

In order to realise this principle, a certification programme is developed as early as the conceptual design stage, which covers all types of work.

The end-to-end certification programme should include: development of models, test benches and other facilities, development or modification of research methods, modelling, laboratory, bench and flight testing with assessment of compliance of the aircraft and its equipment with airworthiness standards, development and implementation of flight test technology, execution of proof documentation and conformity tables and finally submission of materials to the certification body to obtain an airworthiness certificate.

In the framework of certification programme, the initial set of requirements to the characteristics of the developed product, laid down in the Technical Specifications and Specifications, is presented in the form of control table, which is a systematised matrix of requirements that defines the limits of functional parameters of the product and its equipment in various modes of standard operation. Such parameters primarily include safety, reliability, electromagnetic, software, metrological and other types of compatibility and interchangeability. Based on the control table, a requirements verification matrix is developed, in which methods of verification (analytical calculations, modelling, comparison with peer products, tests), fulfilment of these requirements and criteria of conformity confirmation are to be formulated.

The most important procedure for implementing the principle of 'end-to-end' certification is verification, which is increasingly used worldwide, mainly in the verification and assessment of the results of design and development work at the initial stage of creating new technology.

This procedure is practically the only way to verify the correctness of technical decisions under conditions of a high degree of uncertainty in the initial stages of design, when elements of the designed products have not yet been manufactured and their testing is not possible. The verification of newly developed component designs and processes, product quality improvement measures and the evaluation of the results of these measures are subject to verification.

Verification can be based on analytical studies, calculations, mathematical and physical modelling, analysis of input data, design, technological and operational documentation, comparison with prototype counterparts, etc.

Based on the results of verification, preventive measures are developed and implemented in order to eliminate the non-conformities identified and thereby improve the reliability and safety of the products. To prove the effectiveness of preventive measures, they are in turn subjected to verification procedures.

Documented verification results are used at product certification completion as evidence along with ground and flight test results, statistical data on product quality of manufacture and operation, failure study results and evaluation of effectiveness of reliability and safety improvement measures.

The next stage of 'end-to-end' certification, carried out in the early stages of development, can include laboratory and bench testing.

In order to make the laboratory-benchmark tests certifiable, the methods and means of conducting these tests should also be subjected to verification procedures. The effectiveness of the "end-to-end" certification process is characterised by the degree of readiness of the certification

documentation, which should be more than 50% of the total required by the start of flight tests.

Flight tests, which play an important role in domestic practice for assessing the main characteristics of an aircraft and establishing its compliance with airworthiness standards, are generally of considerably less importance abroad. The implementation in practice of the "test everything before flight" principle makes it possible to obtain up to 80% of all characteristics on the ground.

In foreign practice, the flight test period is not regarded as a formative, cognitive phase, but only as a test, a scoring phase. The focus is only on those tests which cannot be simulated under ground conditions. The results of flight tests usually give a 5-7% discrepancy with the simulation and ground test results.

The use of 'end-to-end' aircraft certification is also economically viable. It is known that the cost of one rework at the modelling, flight test bench and flight test stages is in the ratio of 1:10:100.

Foreign firms refer the design and development of a certification programme to serious engineering work carried out by designers and a dedicated service (the division responsible for coordinating certification work). For example, the described approach to certification of the Boeing 747 wide-body aircraft made it possible to carry out their refinement and certification flight tests in one year. The published materials show that its overall certification programme was set up from the beginning of the design and included a phased implementation of work as each section of the project was completed (Figure 2). The firm developed a certification manual based on experience from previous aircraft, customer contacts, and adherence to US FAR (Federal Aviation Regular) [1].

The Boeing 747 certification programme includes the establishment of a simulation and test facility, ground testing and flight testing. The overall test programme, including preliminary design, will last more than four years.

The certification process for Boeing 747 and L-1011 aircraft depends on the extent to which the certification documentation is ready. Certification preparation is carried out from the beginning of design and by the beginning of flight testing, it reaches more than 50% of the total volume. At the same time, the pace of obtaining the necessary documentation increases dramatically in the second year of aircraft development (when all test benches are already in operation) and continues throughout the flight test phase, which lasts about a year.

A characteristic feature of the work at all stages of development is their focus on consistent completion of the items of the conformity tables, i.e. proof (by methods of analysis, statistical data, working technical documentation, test results) of compliance of STS characteristics with the requirements of technical specifications.

МОС - methods for determining compliance, НЛС - aircraft airworthiness standards)

In the area of aviation technology, particular importance must be given to the certification of complex technical systems (CTS), whose failures can have severe and sometimes unpredictable consequences.

Despite the diversity in purpose, composition and conditions of use, all STSs have some basic common features that allow them to be grouped into a single class. These common properties include integrity, emergence, hierarchy and finiteness.

Integrity refers to the purposeful operation of all components of the JTS as a whole in order for the system to fulfil its purpose.

Emergence determines the emergence of STS properties that are not inherent to its components and are caused by the non-additivity of system characteristics, the non-linear relationship between the system characteristics and the characteristics of its components.

Hierarchical structure of the STS is understood as the ability to represent a system as part of a super-system of a higher level of hierarchy and any part of a system as a lower level system.

The finiteness of the STS indicates the finiteness of the resources required to create it, i.e. its feasibility in principle.

In addition to these features, the STS is characterised by its complexity, high cost and multi-purpose nature.

The complexity of the STS is determined by the large number of its possible states. The cost includes the cost of creation, production and operation. The multi-purpose nature of the STS leads to the need to characterise its properties by a number of indicators, the requirements for which are often contradictory.

The forms and methods of certification of complex products differ from traditional approaches used in the certification of simpler equipment.

An analysis of existing foreign certification procedures [4] has shown that the main distinctive feature of STS is the certification orientation of all types of work, starting from the conceptual design stage or the implementation of the 'end-to-end' certification principle. The certification body for complex products is included in certification not at the final stage of production (when the product has already been designed and manufactured), but from the beginning of design. At all stages of development of a prototype product, which include significant amounts of modelling and ground laboratory and bench testing for a wide range of life cycle conditions and factors, it is possible to adjust measures to improve product reliability and safety.

In this case, deficiencies, including non-compliance with norms, regulations and standards, can be discovered at an early stage of the development of the STS, which are easier to remedy before or during the development of the prototype STS than during its testing.

In order to implement this principle, a certification programme is developed at the conceptual design stage, covering all types of work: creation of models; creation of test benches; development and refinement of methods of laboratory, bench and full-scale testing of STS units.

In furtherance of the above approach, it seems advisable to align domestic requirements and norms for laboratory and bench tests with internationally accepted requirements and norms for a developed certification testing system linked to the conditions of market competition and strict quality regulation.

Thus, it is legitimate to conclude that in order to make laboratory bench tests certifiable, methods and means of conducting laboratory bench certification tests must also be subject to verification procedures, i.e. checking and proving (confirming) their compliance with the requirements of regulations, rules and standards for aircraft, aircraft engines and other component parts.

In view of the above, methods of certification testing of the STS and experimental and test facilities should be developed at the initial stage of product development, which will be used to fill in a significant amount of the conformity table during the laboratory bench phase. This work should be completed by the end of the development phase of the working documentation and be part of the documentation in the examination of this working documentation to form an opinion on its compliance with the requirements of codes, regulations and standards

for further approval by the Regulatory Authority.

Once the above activities have been completed, further certification work shall be carried out in accordance with the applicable conformity assessment procedures.

The role of ground testing of aircraft or rocket and space technology units to confirm their performance and the required level of reliability is very important. The further away from the designer's board an unreliability is found,"said Academician A.N. Tupolev, "the more expensive it is". Consequently, even at the initial stage of STS creation, methods of certification testing of STS units and experimental test facilities should be developed, with the help of which a considerable amount of the conformity table will be filled in at the stage of laboratory and bench testing of units.

The theoretical justification for the trend towards reduced flight test volume through increased mathematical modelling and bench-top testing can be shown using the example of a typical automatic control system (ACS) aircraft design technology scheme

The technology for designing aeroplane ACSs is by now largely established [5]. Mathematical support allows selecting and justifying the ACS structure, settings, analyzing the system stability and proving the fulfillment of the control system requirements with a given probability.

Mathematical modelling is used when a sufficiently reliable mathematical description of the process being modelled is known. Of considerable interest is the task of justifying the treatment of the system at various stages of its development and the possibility of moving to the next stage in the process chain.

At each stage of system development, various defects are detected and corrected, i.e. the system is adjusted and refined. In doing so, an improvement in system performance is observed. By defining a failure as any non-compliance of the system's parameters and characteristics with the requirements, and taking into account the probabilistic nature of the defect detection process, we get an opportunity to use the well-known and rather fully developed mathematical apparatus of reliability theory to describe this process. In this case, the event of defect detection is an analogue of failure, the probability of this event is the probability of failure, and the probability of defect-free state of the system is the probability of no-failure operation, i.e. the reliability of the system R .

As the system is being experimentally tested, its "reliability" grows. This growth dynamics is described by some mathematical relationships, the main one being exponential:

$$R_i(t) = a_i - (a_i - R_{oi}) \exp\{-\Theta_i t_i\}$$

where index i denotes the stage of development;

t_i - development time at this stage;

R_{oi} - initial reliability value for this stage;

Θ_i - intensity of detection and elimination of defects at this stage;

a_i - limiting reliability value for this stage, determined by completeness of simulation of system operation conditions at this stage.

The exponential model is justified by the fact that the growth of reliability is proportional to the detected reliability, i.e.

$$\dot{R} = \Theta(a - R)$$

the difference of the parameter a from unity is determined by the occurrence of random failures during the functioning of any system, which do not require improvement of the system.

A study of the growth dynamics of reliability of a wide variety of aerospace systems during their experimental development reveals the following patterns:

the intensity of defect detection decreases with the transition to the next stages, i.e.

$$\Theta_{i-1} > \Theta_i$$

This can be explained both by the reduction in the number of undetected defects and by the

increasing complexity of the defect detection conditions (defects are most easily detected in mathematical modelling, the most difficult in flight tests);

the limit value increases with the transition to the next level, i.e.

$$a_{i-1} < a_i$$

The limit value increases in the next level, i.e. , due to the increasingly complete simulation of real-world operating conditions in the transition from mathematical modelling to flight testing.

As a result, the time-optimal transition from stage to stage can be set and solved, namely:

$$T = t_{i-1} + t_i = \frac{I}{\Theta_{i-1}} \ln \frac{a_{i-1} - R_{oi-1}}{a_{i-1} - R_{oi}} + \frac{I}{\Theta_i} \ln \frac{a_i - R_{oi}}{a_i - R_{oi+1}} = \min R_{oi}$$

The solution to this optimization problem is the condition of equality of reliability growth rates at $i-1$ and i at the transition point R_{oi} , namely:

$$\Theta_i (a_i - R_{oi}) = \Theta_{i-1} (a_{i-1} - R_{oi}) .$$

A similar condition is obtained if the cost of working through the various stages is used instead of time.

Analysis of foreign experience in the development of aviation equipment shows that flight tests, which play an important role in domestic practice to establish compliance with the basic characteristics of the aircraft NGV, abroad have significantly lesser, mainly demonstration value, as up to 80% of all problems arising in the development of the relevant systems are solved on the ground.

This current trend is consistent with the low values of defect detection intensity during the flight test phase and the values of the random reliability component being close to unity.

It follows from the optimum transition condition that the amount of flight testing required to rectify previously undetected defects is close to zero, and the aim becomes only to demonstrate the results achieved.

The accumulated domestic experience [1] of many years of research on creation and development by mathematical modelling of computational systems of aircraft guidance makes it possible to analyse the work of all on-board equipment in a complex under the action of all possible navigation errors on piloting accuracy, allows to state full compliance of processes of creation of aircraft models with global development trends.

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